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An Efficient Feature Extraction Methodology for Computer Vision Applications using Wavelet Compressed Zernike Moments

G. A. Papakostas¹, D. A. Karras², B. G. Mertzios³ and Y. S. Boutalis¹

¹ *Democritus University of Thrace, Department of Electr. and Comp. Eng.,
67100 Xanthi, Greece,
gpapakos@ee.duth.gr, ybout@ee.duth.gr*

² *Chalkis Institute of Technology, Automation Dept. and Hellenic Open University,
Rodu 2, Ano Iliupolis, Athens 16342, Greece,
dakarras@teihal.gr, dakarras@ieee.org, dakarras@usa.net*

³ *Technological Institute of Thessaloniki, Greece
mertziios@uom.gr*

Abstract

A new method for extracting feature sets with improved reconstruction and classification performance in computer vision applications is presented in this paper. The main idea is to propose a procedure for obtaining surrogates of the compressed versions of very reliable feature sets without affecting significantly their reconstruction and recognition properties. The surrogate feature vector is of lower dimensionality and thus more appropriate for pattern recognition tasks. The proposed feature extraction method (FEM) combines the advantages of the multiresolution analysis, which is based on the wavelet theory, with the high discriminative nature of Zernike moment sets. The resulted feature vector is used as a classification feature, in order to achieve high recognition rates in a typical pattern recognition system. The results of the experimental study support the validity and the strength of the proposed method.

Keywords *Pattern Recognition, Wavelet Compression, Zernike Moments, Neural Classifier*

1. Introduction

A crucial part of any intelligent imaging system, which learns from its environment and interacts with it, is a pattern recognition process. In general, a pattern recognition process employs four stages: (1) image acquisition (2) image preprocessing (denoising, filtering, etc) (3) feature extraction and finally (4) classification. The third step is perhaps the most significant, since it determines in a high degree the overall performance of the system. A feature extraction method (FEM) can be termed successful if the resulted features describe

uniquely the processed object in a scene. The more successful a FEM is the more efficient the classification is.

Many FEMs that provide several discriminative feature sets have been presented, some of them are based on the computation of an object moments. Moments have been used successfully in many classification applications and their ability to describe an object fully makes them a powerful tool in image processing tasks especially in computer vision applications, like object recognition in robotic applications and object characterization in visual inspection based quality control systems. Among the moment categories used in image processing, Zernike moments constitute a good choice for an object representation [1,2]. Their information redundancy, low noise sensitivity and rotation invariance are the most considerable properties of them. Theoretically, in order to fully describe an object, one should employ a feature vector containing an infinite number of Zernike moments. In practice, it suffices to use a high dimension Zernike feature vector (ZFV), which, however, is not acceptable for pattern recognition tasks since it increases the complexity and the computational burden of the process. In this paper we are proposing a feature extraction method, which results in wavelet-based surrogates of the ZFVs. These surrogates are of lower dimension than their corresponding ZFVs, but they maintain much of the crucial information ZFVs carry. The appropriateness of the surrogate vectors is tested both in reconstruction and in recognition performance. Using appropriately defined indices we compare the performance of the surrogates with the performance of the corresponding ZFVs. It is experimentally shown that the new surrogate vectors significantly outperform the ZFVs of similar dimension. In principle, the proposed

method could be applied not only on ZFVs but also on any other high dimension feature vector.

The presentation of the paper is organized into four sections. Each one of them participates to the implementation and verification of the proposed FEM. In section 2, Zernike moments are presented and the major properties of them are briefly discussed. Moreover, two indices are defined, which can estimate the reconstruction and recognition performance of a ZFV of lower dimension in comparison to the corresponding performance of a ZFV of a standard high dimension. The wavelet theory and especially its compression aspects are presented in section 3. The main method and the corresponding algorithm is described in section 4, while section 5 tests the performance of the method in pattern recognition experiments, using typical neural classifiers. The experimental results justify the usefulness of the novel feature vector, and establish it as a powerful classification feature that guarantees high recognition rates. Section 6 summarizes the main ideas and draws the conclusions.

2. Zernike Moments for Feature Extraction

Moments have been widely used in image processing applications through the years. *Geometrical, central and normalized* moments were for many decades the only family of applied moments. The main disadvantage of these descriptors was their disability to fully describe an object in a way that, using the moments set, the reconstruction of the object could be possible. In other words they weren't orthogonal.

Zernike comes to fill this gap, by introducing a set of complex polynomials, which form a complete orthogonal set over the interior of the unit circle $x^2 + y^2 = 1$. These polynomials [1, 2] have the form

$$V_{nm}(x, y) = V_{nm}(\rho, \vartheta) = R_{nm}(\rho) \exp(jm\vartheta) \quad (1)$$

where n is a non-negative integer and m is a non zero integer subject to the constraints $n-|m|$ even and $|m| \leq n$, ρ is the length of vector from the origin (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) to the pixel (x, y) and θ the angle between vector ρ and x axis in counter-clockwise direction. $R_{nm}(\rho)$, are the Zernike radial polynomials in (ρ, θ) polar coordinates defined as

$$R_{nm}(\rho) = \sum_{s=0}^{n-|m|/2} (-1)^s \frac{(n-s)!}{s! \left(\frac{n+|m|}{2} - s\right)! \left(\frac{n-|m|}{2} - s\right)!} \rho^{n-2s} \quad (2)$$

Note that $R_{n,-m}(\rho) = R_{nm}(\rho)$

The polynomials of Eq. (2) are orthogonal and satisfy the orthogonality principle

$$\iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq 1} [V_{nm}(x, y)]^* V_{pq}(x, y) dx dy = \frac{\pi}{n+1} \delta_{np} \delta_{mq}$$

where $\delta_{\alpha\beta} = 1$ for $\alpha = \beta$ and $\delta_{\alpha\beta} = 0$ otherwise, is the Kronecker symbol.

The Zernike moment of order n with repetition m for a continuous image function $f(x, y)$, that vanishes outside the unit disk is

$$Z_{nm} = \frac{n+1}{\pi} \iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq 1} f(x, y) V_{nm}^*(\rho, \theta) dx dy \quad (3)$$

For a digital image, the integrals are replaced by summations [1,2] to get

$$Z_{nm} = \frac{n+1}{\pi} \sum_x \sum_y f(x, y) V_{nm}^*(\rho, \theta), \quad x^2 + y^2 \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

Suppose that one knows all moments Z_{nm} of $f(x, y)$ up to a given order n_{max} . It is desired to reconstruct a discrete function $\hat{f}(x, y)$ whose moments exactly match those of $f(x, y)$ up to the given order n_{max} . Zernike moments are the coefficients of the image expansion into orthogonal Zernike polynomials. By orthogonality of the Zernike basis

$$\hat{f}(x, y) = \sum_{n=0}^{n_{max}} \sum_m Z_{nm} V_{nm}(\rho, \theta) \quad (5)$$

with m having similar constraints as in (1). Note that as n_{max} approaches infinity $\hat{f}(x, y)$ will approach $f(x, y)$.

According to (2) there are a lot of computations (factorials) that should be carried out, in order to calculate the radial polynomials. For this reason many researchers have introduced methods for fast computation of Zernike moments [3,4]. Among these, the well-known "q-recursive method" [5] is considered to be the more efficient and is used by this paper. The method permits the evaluation of radial polynomials by using recursive equations.

In this paper, where the Zernike moments will be used as object descriptors for classification purposes, a short discussion about their variability under rotation, translation and scaling should be considered.

Since Zernike moments are only rotationally invariant, additional properties of translation and scale invariance should be given to these moments in some way. We can introduce translation invariance in the Zernike moments by converting the absolute pixel coordinates as follows

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} x - X_0 \\ y - Y_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where

$$X_0 = \frac{m_{10}}{m_{00}}, Y_0 = \frac{m_{01}}{m_{00}} \quad (7)$$

are the centroid coordinates of the object (with m denoting the geometrical moment).

Scaling invariance can be achieved by normalizing the Zernike moments with respect to the geometrical moment m_{00} of the object. The resulted moments named *Improved Zernike Moments (IZM)* [6] are derived from the following equation

$$Z'_{nm} = \frac{Z_{nm}}{m_{00}} \quad (8)$$

where Z_{nm} are the Zernike moments of equation (4) that have been computed in accordance to the transformation of (6).

In this way, a set of rotation, scaling and translation invariant, complex moments can be considered. Taking the amplitudes of these complex values, a feature vector can be formed, which in the sequence is used as an input to a classifier system. At this point, the following question arises. Up to which order of the Zernike moments should one compute in order to achieve best representation and high performance of the classification procedure? To quantitatively measure the usefulness of the Zernike feature vector, in respect to the information redundancy and the classification rate, we define the following indices:

Definition 1: *The fitness of a feature vector in respect to its ability to reconstruct the object that describes, can be defined by the DRRE (Dimension Relative Reconstruction Error)*

$$DRRE = \frac{1 - \frac{VectorDimension}{MaxVectorDimension}}{\frac{VectorRecError}{MaxVectorRecError} - 1} \quad (9)$$

where, $VectorDimension$ is the dimension of a feature vector, which is used to reconstruct the image. Its reconstruction performance ($VectorRecError$) is compared with the reconstruction performance ($MaxVectorRecError$) of a Zernike moment vector of a pre-specified maximum dimension $MaxVectorDimension$.

Definition 2: *The fitness of a feature vector in respect to a classification procedure can be defined by the DRPMSE (Dimension Relative Performance MSE (Mean Square Error))*

$$DRPMSE = \frac{1 - \frac{VectorDimension}{MaxVectorDimension}}{\left| \frac{VectorPMSE}{MaxVectorPMSE} - 1 \right|} \quad (10)$$

where, $VectorDimension$ is the dimension of a feature vector, which is used to classify the image. Its classification performance ($VectorPMSE$ – PMSE stands for Performance Mean Squared Error) is compared with the classification performance ($MaxVectorPMSE$) of a Zernike moment vector of a pre-specified maximum dimension $MaxVectorDimension$.

The above performance indices relate the feature vector dimensionality to the error produced when used to reconstruct or classify an object respectively. For practical purposes, a low dimension feature vector that guarantees small classification and reconstruction errors is mostly desired and this is indicated by high values of these indices. The factor $MaxVectorDimension$ in the previous equations is the dimension of a comparative optimum feature vector that produces small errors. In the experiments of section 5 this is set to 256. Any constructed feature vector will be compared with this optimum representation by means of the gain in respect to classification and reconstruction procedures.

In section 4, a method for obtaining Zernike based feature vectors, with reduced dimension and increased ability to describe an object, is presented. The importance of these feature vectors is quantitatively measured by means of the above defined performance indices.

3. Wavelet Compression of Moment Coefficients

The present paper uses an important property of the Wavelet Theory called Multiresolution Representation. The application of wavelets for compression purposes is based on this property. By this property, a signal is viewed at various levels of approximations or resolutions [7]. The coarsest approximation of the signal with the “details” at every level completely represents the original signal. The term *Details* refers to the difference of information between the approximation of the signal at consecutive resolutions k and $k+1$.

The procedure of signal decomposition (*analysis*) into several resolutions and its reconstruction (*synthesis*), can be described by the following equations

$$Synthesis \quad f(t) = \sum_k u_{j_0,k} \cdot \phi_{j_0,k}(t) + \sum_{j=j_0}^{\infty} \sum_k w_{j,k} \cdot \psi_{j,k}(t) \quad (11)$$

and

$$Analysis \quad u_{j,k} = W_{\phi}(f(j,k)), \quad w_{j,k} = W_{\psi}(f(j,k)) \quad (12)$$

where $u_{j,k}$, $w_{j,k}$ are the scaling and wavelet coefficients respectively, j,k are indices of the translation and dilation parameters, j_0 represents the coarsest scale and W_ψ , W_ϕ

$$W_\psi \left(f \left(k2^{-s}, 2^{-s} \right) \right) = 2^{s/2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) \cdot \psi \left(2^s t - k \right) dt \quad (13)$$

the *mother wavelet* (ψ) and the *scaling function* (ϕ) wavelet transforms.

In the above equations the indices j,k correspond to the translation and dilation parameters and j_0 to the coarsest scale. The scaling and wavelet coefficients can be considered as the coefficients of a lowpass (L in Figure 1) and highpass (H in Figure 1) filter, respectively. By this definition the procedures of one level decomposition and reconstruction of a signal involving MRA (Multi Resolution Analysis) algorithm, can be described as illustrated in the following figure [7, 8]:

Figure 1. One level decomposition-reconstruction, "quadrature mirror filter"

Thus, the first stage of the MRA decomposition (coarsest level =1) produces a lowpass component c^1_n referred to as the smoothed or approximation version of $s(n)$, since its resolution is half of $s(n)$ (downsampling by 2) and the detail or difference component d^1_n (outcome of the highpass filter H downsampled by 2) which contains the high frequency details of $s(n)$ that are not in c^1_n . This first level MRA Reconstruction is given by the following formula (in accordance also to (11)-(13))

$$s(t) = \sum_{n=0..M} c^1_n \cdot \phi_{1,n}(t) + \sum_{n=0..M} d^1_n \cdot \psi_{1,n}(t) \quad (14)$$

With $\Psi_{1,n} = 1/\sqrt{2} \Psi(t/2-n)$ all translates n of the mother wavelet spanning the detail subspace D^1 .

Signal compression using wavelets is applicable in many signal, image and multimedia processing systems. The main idea is based on the multiresolution representation of the processed signal and on the process, where some coefficients d^1_k in equation (14) above, that describe the signal details, are rejected by thresholding. Since the details constitute only the high frequency components of the signal, one can conclude that the resulted compressed signal slightly differs from the original one.

The present paper makes use of this idea to compress a 1-D signal. Then the remaining wavelet coefficients form a feature vector, which is used in pattern classification tasks. Thresholding is invoked by using a simple soft

thresholding (shrinkage) procedure described in [9] and as implemented in MatlabR11 it can be described by the following formula

$$Y = \begin{cases} \text{sign}(x)(|x| - thr) & , |x| > thr \\ 0 & , |x| \leq thr \end{cases}$$

where x is the input signal, Y is its compressed version and thr the threshold. Soft thresholding is an extension of hard thresholding, first setting to zero the elements whose absolute values are lower than the threshold, and then shrinking the nonzero coefficients towards 0.

It is obvious from (14) above that such a compression procedure is lossy since the detail subspace D^1 of the MRA signal representation will be not recovered perfectly from missing samples d^1_k and therefore, small errors (due to d^1_k being high frequency components of $s(t)$) will be introduced in the reconstruction.

Another approach to this compression procedure would be to leave out all d^1_k with $k > P$. P is defined by the previously decided wavelet coefficient compression ratio. If, for instance, soft thresholding leaves out K detail coefficients, then $P = M - K$ (see eq. (14)) and we leave out $d^1_{M-K+1} \dots d^1_M$ by zeroing them. This latter compression approach, which leaves out the largest translate coefficients of the mother wavelet in the high frequency subspace of $s(n)$ - let's call it truncate by position compression, could be used more effectively for pattern recognition applications, while the soft/hard thresholding approach is used for image reconstruction. In the image reconstruction experiments of section 5 both compression approaches give similar reconstruction error results (although this happens in the computer vision applications of section 5 it may not happen in other cases of image compression, as for instance in natural scenery images) but we present the soft thresholding results, since it is widely employed in wavelet compression literature [7],[8],[9]. In the pattern recognition experiments of section 5, however, only the truncate by position compression approach could be involved.

In this way, using either approach of the above, we obtain a truncated set of coefficients from which the original signal can be approximately reconstructed.

4. The Proposed Feature Extraction Methodology

As mentioned in section 3, once we decide to use Zernike moments as the discriminating features of an object, we have to take a decision about the number of the features to use. The larger the moment order is computed the more image information is captured and theoretically speaking, if the moment order is computed to the infinity the whole image information derives. However, for practical reasons, a low dimension feature vector is desired, which, in turn, implies that only few moment orders would be computed and used. In the sequel we propose a method for generating a feature

vector of the same significance with a Zernike feature vector, but with smaller dimension.

Let Zernike moments (IZM in accordance with (8)) be computed up to order p and repetition q (i.e. $Z'_{00}, Z'_{11}, \dots, Z'_{pq}$). We form a 1-D “moment signal” by using the magnitudes of a fixed number of Zernike moments, arranged in the same order they are computed. That is,

$$\text{Moment Signal } S = \{ |Z'_{20}|, |Z'_{22}|, |Z'_{31}|, \dots, |Z'_{pq}| \} \quad (15)$$

where the Zernike moments Z'_{00} and Z'_{11} are excluded from this signal because they are constant [1] for all objects and thus they do not constitute discriminative quantities.

Instead of using the image itself in a 2-D space, from now on the above signal will represent the original image as a kind of its signature. In this 1-D signal a wavelet compression by a one level decomposition, followed by thresholding is being applied, in order to reduce the dimensionality of the Zernike moment vector. The information redundancy of the resulted compressed signal is tested by means of its performance in reconstruction. The set of wavelet coefficients, which remain after compressing the wavelet signal, is used as the reduced feature vector. The classification usefulness of this vector is investigated, by using a simple neural classifier and the recognition performance is compared with the corresponding performance that other feature vectors give. Also, the performance indices $DRRE$ and $DRPMSE$ defined in section 3 come to prove the efficiency of these features for the test cases that are considered. Figure 2 depicts the steps of the procedure and the two test cases, where the above indices are computed.

The application of the wavelet compression to the 1-D moment signal affects only its details, which correspond to its high frequency components. Therefore, it is expected that, the final Zernike-based feature vector, will have reduced dimension in comparison to the original Zernike vector, without causing significant loss of useful information, due to the application of the compression to the signal details that consists its high frequency component.

The following diagram of figure 2 can illustrate the above procedures that investigate the proposed idea of applying wavelet compression on a set of extracted discriminative features. In this diagram, *Test Case 1* refers to the measurement of the reconstruction performance of the method, while *Test Case 2* refers to the measurement of its classification performance.

The algorithm [10] that performs the procedure is shown in Figure 2, and is summarized as follows:

Figure 2. The proposed algorithm and the verification procedures (test cases 1 and 2)

The Proposed Algorithm

- ❑ Taking a 2-D binary image, we transform the image coordinates in such a way, that the image is mapped to a unit disk [-1,1].
- ❑ Transform the image density function $f(x,y)$ to a translation and scale invariant version using equations (6) and (8) respectively. At this step we get the $g(x,y)$ intensity function.
- ❑ Computation of Zernike moment magnitudes using equation (4). Using these measurements, we construct a one-dimensional signal (14), which consists of those magnitudes. The way to place the magnitudes is the number of generation of each magnitude, which also constitutes the order that each moment participates in the reconstruction procedure.
- ❑ Decomposition of the “moment signal” using equation (11) and the wavelet transform (13), results to a set of wavelet

coefficients (12) able to reconstruct the original “moment signal”.

- At the last step we perform a compression procedure onto the set of wavelet coefficients, by discarding appropriate number of wavelet coefficients belonging to the detailed signal component.

This way a set of wavelet coefficients is obtained. This set can be used to reconstruct the compressed moment signal and consequently the original image signal. It can also directly be used as a feature vector for classification purposes. In the following section, an exhaustive experimental study is taking place, to prove that the resulted wavelet feature vector encloses enough information to reconstruct the compressed Zernike moment signal and from this the original signal, without significant reconstruction error. This wavelet feature vector will also be used as an input to a simple neural classifier performing a typical classification task.

5. Experimental Study

In order to justify the usefulness of the proposed method, a set of experiments have been carried out and their results are presented in this section. All of them belong in the field of computer vision applications since, as we explained in the introduction, moments constitute a powerful tool for such applications. Robotic vision applications, including object recognition and handling, as well as visual inspection quality control systems applications, including defect detection, are some of the most prominent examples of such applications. The experiments presented below are related to object recognition for robotic control applications. Experiments are divided in two types, (1) those by which the reconstruction capability of the wavelet feature vector is established (Test Case 1 of Fig.2) and (2) those which demonstrate its class separability into a classification procedure (Test Case 2 Fig.2).

To perform the experiments some test objects (patterns) are initially selected. Figure 3.b shows a wooden pyramidal puzzle, which is used for robot vision tasks in the Control Systems Lab of DUTH. The 9 parts of the puzzle, placed in arbitrary positions, are shown in figure 3.a. The (256x256) images of these parts are the initial nine patterns of our experiments.

Figure 3. The nine work pieces that are placed (a) in arbitrary positions on the table and (b) on a 3-D truncated pyramid.

Test Case 1

To study the reconstruction capability of the wavelet feature vector the steps of the algorithm of section 4 are executed in reverse order. Figure 2 shows a flow diagram of this procedure. After the wavelet feature vector is truncated (compressed) the algorithm is executed in reverse order, performing the following tasks. 1) One-level wavelet reconstruction and computation of the moment signal, 2) Apply equation (4) for computing the estimated image intensity function using the Zernike moments 3) appropriate thresholding and binarization for the optical evaluation of the reconstructed binary image. The reconstructed image is now in a form suitable for comparison with the original one.

For the computation of the reconstruction normalized error, the following formula is used [11], just after task 2 above is completed

$$\text{Normalized Reconstruction Error } \bar{e}^2 = \frac{\sum_i \sum_j [f(i, j) - \hat{f}(i, j)]^2}{\sum_i \sum_j [f(i, j)]^2} \quad (16)$$

where $f(i, j)$ is the intensity function of the original image and $\hat{f}(x, y)$ the intensity function of the reconstructed one.

For the present experiments, for each of the nine test patterns, the Zernike moments up to the 30th order (256 moments) are computed. The obtained moment signal consists of 256 moment values and is compressed by using the *Haar* wavelet. After compression, a feature vector of 192 wavelet coefficients, by which we can reconstruct the compressed Zernike moment signal, is formed.

An example of the moment signal and the reconstructed moment signal after compressing the wavelet coefficients (in the figure termed ‘compressed’), for one of the patterns, constructed up to 20th Zernike order is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Original Vs Compressed moment signal

The reduced size wavelet feature vector describes the compressed Zernike moment signal. To investigate its reconstruction performance, for all 9 patterns a comparison between the following errors is made: a) the reconstruction error obtained by the 256 original Zernike moments, b) the reconstruction error obtained using only the wavelet feature vector of size 192 and c) the reconstruction error that is obtained using the original 196 Zernike moments, which have been derived computing them up to the 26th order.

The reason for presenting the 196 Zernike moments (up to the 26th order), comes by the fact that the compressed Zernike moments approximated by the 192 wavelet coefficients, seem not only to be more efficient (in vector size) than the original 256 original moments, but also more efficient (in reconstruction error) than a set of moments with similar length. This means that the reduced size wavelet feature vector contains information of higher order than the 26th. Additionally, for each case the reconstruction performance index (9) is evaluated by considering the *Max Vector* to be 256, which is the length of the uncompressed Zernike moment vector (computed up to the 30th order).

Table 1. Images reconstruction statistics

	256 Zernike Moments	196 Zernike Moments	192 Wavelet Coefficients
	Normalized Rec.Error/ (DRRE)	Normalized Rec.Error/ (DRRE)	Normalized Rec.Error/ (DRRE)
	0.1653/ (-)	0.1923/ (1.4349)	0.1661/ (51.6562)
	0.1741/ (-)	0.1911/ (2.4003)	0.1748/ (62.1785)
	0.1542/ (-)	0.1614/ (5.0195)	0.1560/ (21.4167)
	0.2652/ (-)	0.2765/ (5.5005)	0.2667/ (44.2000)
	0.1637/ (-)	0.1726/ (4.3109)	0.1641/ (102.3125)
	0.1992/ (-)	0.2091/ (4.7159)	0.2044/ (9.5769)
	0.2070/ (-)	0.2138/ (7.1346)	0.2107/ (13.9864)
	0.1264/ (-)	0.1445/ (1.6367)	0.1277/ (24.3077)

	0.2440/ (-)	0.2687/ (2.3153)	0.2463/ (26.5217)
AVERAGE VALUES	0.1888/ (-)	0.2033/ (3.8300)	0.1907/ (39.5730)

Looking through table 1, it can be remarked that, the average value of the normalized reconstruction error for all patterns, in the case of the wavelet features, is less than that of the 26th order moment set. Moreover, the reconstruction error, when the wavelet features are used, is closer to the reconstruction error obtained using the uncompressed 256 Zernike moments. Thus, the set of 192 wavelet coefficients encloses more information than the set of the 196 Zernike moments. Actually, its information content is very close to this of the set of 256 Zernike moments, while its size is reduced by 25%. The effectiveness of the wavelet features can be also justified by comparing the average values of the performance index DRRE (9), as depicted in Table 1. This index measures the gain in dimension reduction in relation to the loss in reconstruction accuracy. The value of the index becomes large when the number of the used coefficients becomes small, while at the same time the reconstruction error is kept close to the reconstruction error produced by the use of uncompressed 256 moments. Thus, the higher the values of this index the better the performance of the reduced size vector is. Figure 5 illustrates the average (for the nine patterns) normalized reconstruction error with respect to the number of moments used for the reconstruction. The dashed curve represents the error curve that corresponds to the reconstruction by compressed Zernike moments, approximated by the wavelet coefficients and the solid one corresponds to the error for the original uncompressed Zernike moments. This figure demonstrates that the proposed wavelet features carries enough image information to reconstruct the pattern, with minimum error and is more efficient than the uncompressed Zernike moments of the same size. The fact that the derived set of wavelet coefficients has better reconstruction capabilities than the same number of Zernike moments is of major importance. This property is very useful especially for classification tasks, where the number of "good" [1] discriminative features has to be kept as low as possible.

Although, Zernike moments are not the most powerful family of orthogonal moments, as has been proved in [11], it was decided to apply the presented method to these moments, with considerable results, because of their popularity. However, the proposed method is generic and can be applied to any moment signal. To demonstrate this, this method has been also applied to two other kinds of orthogonal moments the pseudo-Zernike (PZMs) [11] and orthogonal Fourier-Mellin moments (OFMMs) [12]. The results presented in Figure 6, are of the same significance as in the case of Zernike

moments, which establish the proposed idea as a general procedure for feature extraction.

Figure 5. Normalized Reconstruction error of (a) uncompressed Zernike moments (solid line) and (b) compressed Zernike moments represented by wavelet coefficients (dashed line)

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Normalized Reconstruction error of (a) Pseudo-Zernike Moments and (b) orthogonal Fourier-Mellin Moments

In Figure 6, the normalized reconstruction error for the case of (a) PZMs up to the 20th order (231 moments) and (b) OFMMs up to the 20th order (441 moments) is presented in comparison with their compressed ones.

The proposed method does not depend on the type or the kind of the image to be processed. Although, the present paper is limited to object images as part of a robot vision system, it can be mentioned that the reconstruction of a more general image by a set of compressed Zernike moments, is also attainable. In Figure 7, a common benchmark image, the Lena image, is used to justify the effectiveness of the proposed method of reconstructing any image by a set of compressed features. A 64x64 size Lena image is used, and the reconstruction is made by using a set of moments computed up to the 45th order (552 moments). Figure 7a shows the original grey image. Figure 7b shows the reconstructed image after using the 552 uncompressed Zernike moments. The normalized reconstruction error was measured to be 0.1497. Figure 7c shows the reconstructed image after the compressed Zernike moments (with 25% less features) was used. The normalized reconstruction error was measured to be 0.1507. Thus, a 25% reduction of the feature set that describes the test image has not caused significant loss of image information, since the resulted error is quite similar to this of the uncompressed feature set.

It seems that Zernike moments are not the most appropriate for representing detailed grey level images since one should employ a very large set of moments to achieve perfect reconstruction. An exhaustive examination of the performance of various orthogonal moment families in combination with the proposed method for representing detailed grey level images could be the subject of future work.

Figure 7. (a) Original image, (b) Reconstructed image by the uncompressed Zernike moments up to the 45th order (552 moments) and (c) Reconstructed image by the compressed Zernike moments of the same order (26% fewer features).

Test Case 2

In the second test case, a study about the classification capabilities of the novel wavelet feature vector, which describes the compressed Zernike moment signal, is performed. Three typical feature vectors are compared one another in relation to their classification performance. The first vector contains the Zernike moments up to the order of 6, which yields 14 moments

(the first two are excluded). The second vector contains 10 wavelet coefficients representing the compressed Zernike moment signal, the uncompressed version of which contained the Zernike moments up to the order of 6. The compression of the wavelet coefficients is made by using the ‘truncate by position’ approach mentioned in section 3. It is decided to use these features of 6th order instead of 30th order because the resulting feature vector is considered sufficient for this kind of classification purposes. The third vector contains the 10 uncompressed Zernike moments (the first two are excluded), computed up to the 5th order.

After a typical cross-validation procedure [13] it was decided, the classifier to be a typical multilayer perceptron containing 1 hidden layer, with 10 hidden neurons and 9 (equal to the number of classes) output neurons. The number of inputs equals the number of the features used in each case. The learning set contains 324 images. They were produced by using the following procedure. The original 9 image objects were transformed by combining various scaling, translation, and rotation operations to produce 54 images including the original ones). Adding noise and blurring the previous 54 images, 540 more images were generated. In fact, Gaussian noise of 6 levels from 0-25% (this value corresponds to the percent number of the image pixels that have been affected by the noise) and blurring effect of 10 blurring radius 0-9 (the radius determines the width of the edge that is blurred) generated these noisy images. 270 noisy images randomly selected from the set of the above 540 images plus the 54 uncorrupted images were used to form the 324 images training set. The rest 270 degraded images were used for testing.

Before evaluating the classification performance of the proposed surrogate wavelet features, we conducted a reconstruction experiment to test their appropriateness in describing degraded (by noise and blur) images. Table 2 contains the same indices presented in table 1, but for the respective worst case distorted (maximum noise (25%) – maximum blurring (radius 9)) objects. Examining the normalized reconstruction error and the DRRE index, it can be observed that the wavelet coefficient surrogates are still able to carry information which is otherwise carried by uncompressed Zernike features of larger dimension, although the images are now severely corrupted.

Table 2. Noisy images reconstruction statistics

	256 Zernike Moments	196 Zernike Moments	192 Wavelet Coefficients
	Normalized Rec.Error/ (DRRE)	Normalized Rec.Error/ (DRRE)	Normalized Rec.Error/ (DRRE)
	0.2541/ (-)	0.2557/ (37.2217)	0.2542/ (635.2500)

	0.2014/ (-)	0.2117/ (4.5828)	0.2082/ (7.4044)
	0.1677/ (-)	0.1773/ (4.0942)	0.1708/ (13.5242)
	0.2523/ (-)	0.2616/ (6.3583)	0.2588/ (9.7038)
	0.1738/ (-)	0.1788/ (8.1469)	0.1798/ (7.2416)
	0.2217/ (-)	0.2310/ (5.5872)	0.2222/ (110.8500)
	0.2239/ (-)	0.2318/ (6.6426)	0.2294/ (10.1773)
	0.1472/ (-)	0.1551/ (4.3671)	0.1475/ (122.6667)
	0.2650/ (-)	0.2726/ (8.1723)	0.2703/ (12.5000)
AVERAGE VALUES	0.2119/ (-)	0.2195/ (9.4637)	0.2157/ (103.2576)

The neural classifier is trained using the backpropagation learning algorithm. The learning curves for each of the feature vectors are shown in Figure 8. It can be observed that, all feature sets yield a sufficient learning *Mean Square Error* (MSE), with the 6th order Zernike set (14 features) giving lower value than the wavelet one (10 features). This observation itself implies that uncompressed Zernike moments are more efficient than the corresponding reduced size wavelet coefficients, although at the end of the learning procedure, these values are close to each other. However, the MSE of learning with the 10 wavelet features is significantly less than the MSE of learning with the uncompressed 5th order Zernike moments, which has the same vector size (10 features).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8. Training curves of (a) 6th order Zernike moments feature vector, (b) wavelet feature vector corresponding to compressed 6th order Zernike moments and (c) Zernike moments of 5th order

In order to investigate the generalization performance of the trained neural classifier, the testing set of the 270 noisy images, was used. Since the classifier is being used in generalization mode, there is a need to measure its generalization ability. For this reason, the feature vectors of the corresponding test images are presented to the input layer of the trained neural network and the Performance Mean Square Error (PMSE) is computed by using equation (17).

$$PMSE = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_M \sum_N (y_i - d_i)^2 \quad (17)$$

where M is the number of testing patterns (for our experiments this is equal to 270), N the number of classifier outputs and $(y_i - d_i)$ the difference between each classifier output and its corresponding desired value (target).

The observed measures of the three vectors are presented in Table 3. The MSE measurement in Table 3, corresponds to the mean square error measured during the training procedure and its analytical expression is the same as equation (17), where M is equal to the number of training patterns.

Table 3. Performance Mean Square Error, classification rate and the DRPMSE index for Zernike feature vectors and wavelet based surrogate.

	Number of Features	MSE	PMSE	Classification Rate (%)	DRPMSE
Zernike Features of 6 th order	14	1.04×10^{-3}	0,8775	100	-
Wavelet Features	10	2.76×10^{-3}	0,8718	100	43,9850
Zernike Features of 5 th order	10	5.27×10^{-2}	0,9213	88.88	5,7241

Considering the results of Table 3 and the learning curves of Fig.6, it is concluded that in the case of the 6th order Zernike moment vector, neural network presents an overfitting behavior in comparison to the wavelet vector, since, even if it has smaller MSE, the PMSE is bigger. The overfitting phenomenon is caused by the use of more complex networks than actually required by the training data, where the adjustable variables are plenty [13].

Thus, the usage of the wavelet vector, which size is almost 25% less than the Zernike moment vector, somehow prevents the classifier from overfitting. In conjunction with the fact that this vector presents similar learning curve with the original vector, its usefulness and high efficiency can be established.

In case the proposed method is applied in combination with other orthogonal moment sets, like pseudo Zernike and Fourier Mellin, it is expected to present the same classification behavior. This is fully justified by the fact that as it was shown in the reconstruction experiments the surrogate wavelet features describing the compressed pseudo Zernike or Fourier Mellin moment signal they still carry information which corresponds to the uncompressed moments of larger vector size.

6. Conclusions

An innovative feature extraction method (FEM) is presented in this paper, for computer vision applications. The FEM is based on wavelet features that describe a compressed Zernike moment signal. The resulting

feature vector offers a solution to the two conflicted demands of any pattern recognition system, namely, the need for low dimension and at the same time rich in information representation. These compressed features are able to describe an object by means of information that belongs to higher resolutions. In other words, the available image information in high frequencies is captured and packed (compressed) into a feature vector with low dimension. In this way, applying 25% compression on the moment signal, the effectiveness of the wavelet vector is justified using two test cases. In one case, the vector is compared with the uncompressed Zernike moments of the same order and with the ones of one order lower, by means of the information it carries with respect to the reconstruction error. At the second case the three test vectors are used as inputs to a neural classifier for training and classification purposes. The results of both experiments are very promising and display that, by compressing the image information in the spectral domain, a reduction of the dimension of the descriptive feature vector can be achieved, while maintaining almost intact its information content and its classification ability.

Future work about the performance of different wavelet families to the proposed method must be carried out, in order to present results, already mentioned. Finally, a comparison between the performance of different compression methods (DCT, STFT etc.) will be very useful, which in conjunction with the other tests can establish the proposed method as an generic FEM.

7. References

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